

ACADEMIC SUPERVISION MANAGEMENT USING GUIDANCE PRINCIPLES IN IMPROVING PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCIES (DESCRIPTIVE STUDY ON PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE AT SDN 205 NEGLASARI, BANDUNG CITY)

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Abstract

The general aim of this research is to describe academic supervision management using the principles of guidance in improving pedagogical competence at SDN 205 Neglasari, Bandung City. The specific objectives are to describe: 1) Planning academic supervision using the principles of guidance in increasing pedagogical competence, 2) Carrying out academic supervision using the principles of guidance in increasing pedagogical competence, 3) Carrying out academic supervision using the principles of guidance in improving pedagogical competence, 4) Monitoring academic supervision using guidance principles in improving pedagogical competence. This research method is descriptive qualitative and the data collection techniques are interviews, observation and documentation. The research subjects were school principals and teachers. The research results show that planning, organizing, implementing and supervising the improvement of teachers' pedagogical competence is effective.

Keywords: Academic Supervision Management, Increasing Pedagogical Competency.

INTRODUCTION

The world of education in Indonesia is certainly inseparable from government policies, including Permendikbud Number 13 of 2007 which states that a school principal must master the School Principal Competency Standards which consist of personality competence, managerial competence, supervision competence, entrepreneurial competence and social competence. Likewise, a teacher is required to master pedagogical competence, personality competence, social competence and professional competence in accordance with Government Regulation Number 19 of 2005, concerning Standards for Educators and Education Personnel which states that Educators must have academic qualifications and competence as learning agents, be physically healthy and spiritual and have the ability to realize national education goals. Education is a conscious effort to prepare participants through guidance, teaching and/or training activities for their future roles. Education is said to be successful if it is able to produce students with the maximum level of personal achievement. This measure can be shown through student learning outcomes in the form of learning achievement. According to Law No. 2023 concerning National Education or the National Education System Law, it is the legal basis for managing education in Indonesia.

According to George R. Terry, management is the achievement of predetermined goals using the activities of other people. Henry Fayol as contained in his book *General Industrial Management* defines management as a certain process consisting of planning, organizing,

mobilizing human resources and supervising human resources in order to achieve goals. Sudjana means that management is a series of various reasonable activities carried out by a person based on established norms and in their implementation they are related and interrelated, these are carried out by a person or several people within the organization and are given the task of carrying out these activities.

George R. Terry in his book *The Principles of Management* as quoted by Sukarna (2011:10) divides four basic functions of management, namely planning (*planing*), organizing (*organizing*), mobilization / implementation (*actuating*), and supervision (*controlling*). These four management functions are abbreviated as POAC.

Observing the opinions of these experts, performance can be interpreted as the level of work results in terms of quality and quantity achieved by human resources or members of the organization in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to them based on performance standards that have been set during a certain period within the framework of achieving organization goals.

Etymologically, the term supervision comes from English and consists of two root words, namely "super" which means above, and "vision" which means "to see", so overall supervision is defined as looking from above. With that understanding, supervision is defined as activities carried out by supervisors and school principals as officials whose position is above or higher than the teacher, to see and supervise the teacher's work. Experts according to several experts define supervision as follows: Kimball Wiles, in Maryono, states that "supervision is assistance in the development of a better teaching-learning situation." Supervision is a process of assistance to improve the teaching and learning situation to make it better. This understanding shows that supervision is a process of assistance, guidance and coaching by supervisors to teachers who improve the learning process.

Principal supervision is part of ongoing educational supervision within the scope of learning activities carried out by teachers, so it is appointed to improve the quality of learning processes and outcomes.

Guidance in the English dictionary comes from the word guide which can mean showing the way, leading, guiding, giving instructions, organizing, directing and giving advice. Donald G. Mortensen and Alan M. Schmuller understand guidance as part of the educational component that provides and provides special services for students to develop their abilities and competencies.

Etymologically, the term counseling comes from Latin, namely "*consilium*" which means "with" or "together" which is combined with "accept" or "understand". Meanwhile, in Anglo-Saxon, the term counseling comes from "*sellan*" which means "handing over" or "conveying" Shertzer and Stone explain that counseling is a process of individual interaction to provide an understanding of themselves and their environment in determining the goals that will be carried out based on the values they adhere to.

The formulation of the principles of guidance and counseling in general is related to service targets, client problems, objectives and problem handling processes, service programs, service delivery. These principles include:

1. Principles regarding service targets
2. Principles regarding service programs.
3. Principles of guidance in schools in the operational field of guidance.

Pedagogical competency is the ability to manage student learning which includes understanding the insights or foundations of education, understanding students, developing curriculum, designing learning, implementing educational and dialogical learning, utilizing learning technology, evaluating learning outcomes and developing student development to actualize the various potentials they have.

Academic supervision activities in the city of Bandung, especially at SDN 205 Neglasari, show conditions where education or teachers still have not mastered pedagogical competence. In carrying out their duties, the principal has not yet fully created a supervision program that suits the school's needs due to a lack of understanding.

The academic supervision carried out by the school principal is sufficient, however, when problems encountered during supervision are not immediately followed up by the school principal. Therefore, in order to carry out the duties of the Principal as Supervisor, it is necessary to prepare a supervision program that comprehensively and systematically describes the planned activities to be carried out and what follow-up will be to the results of supervision after the activities are carried out so that there can be significant improvements in academic supervision activities at SDN 205 Neglasari Bandung.

In relation to the academic supervision program, a school principal who is successful in carrying out academic supervision is called a quality school principal, however if the supervision program is not of good quality then the school principal is of less quality. SDN 205 Neglasari, Bandung City, based on observations or observations of researchers, has shown the performance of the principal in creating an academic supervision program in improving the pedagogic competence of teachers at SDN 205 Neglasari.

Based on the results of the 2023 Teacher Competency Test (UKG) at SDN 205 Neglasari, Bandung City, it was found that the results were still low, of the 14 teachers, 6 were already qualified, and 8 (not yet qualified) people (or 43%) were developing. 57% are not feasible and not yet feasible, meaning that the competency of the teachers at SDN 205 Neglasari is still far away or still low. This suggests that teaches' pedagogical competence is still low. The following is data obtained from the UKG results of SDN 205 Neglasari.

The results of initial interviews with the school principal and deputy head of curriculum, they revealed that the workshops or training activities that had been participated in so far were still not optimal because they were still theoretical, not necessary and were not followed up by monitoring by the school principal. So it still seems that they have not been able to improve pedagogical competence.

Imam Mughnil Anam's (2019) research entitled Management of Increasing Teacher Pedagogical Competency at MTs Al-Wathoniyah Semarang. This research aims to produce effective and efficient guidance and counseling management to improve teacher pedagogical competence at MTs Al-Wathoniyah. This type of research is descriptive qualitative research with data collection methods. The research results show effective and efficient guidance and counseling management to improve the pedagogical competence of teachers at MTs Al-Wathoniyah.

Based on the background presented above, the formulation of the problem in this research is: Raw input for this research is the teacher. The research process that will be studied is Academic Supervision Management Using Guidance Principles in Improving Pedagogical Competence at SDN 205 Neglasari Bandung. With academic supervision management, ultimately how academic supervision management can improve teachers' pedagogical competence well. The research process that will be carried out is related to the management of academic supervision in improving pedagogical competence. The implementation of academic supervision management is something that is observed in relation to teacher pedagogical competence.

Instrumental Input What will be the source of the study is the Government Policy regarding Educational goals which is conveyed through various Education articles from government regulations. Government policy regarding the management of academic supervision is primarily concerned with the learning process achieved.

Environmental Input comes from government policy, in this case the Bandung City education office, regarding supervision management and teacher pedagogical competence that must be prepared or carried out by schools. The teacher's background is an external environmental influence that influences the learning process. So that the discussion in this scientific paper is focused, this paper has problem limitations, namely: 1) Planning Academic Supervision Management Using Guidance Principles in Improving Pedagogical Competence at SDN 205 Neglasari, Bandung City 2) Organizing Academic Supervision Management Using Principles - Guidance Principles in Improving Pedagogical Competence at SDN 205 Neglasari, Bandung City 3) Implementation of Academic Supervision Management using Guidance Principles in Improving Pedagogical Competency at SDN 205 Neglasari Bandung City 4) Supervision of Academic Supervision Management using Guidance Principles in Improving Pedagogical Competence studying at SDN 205 Neglasari, Bandung City.

This research is aimed at getting an overview of the implementation of Academic Supervision management in Improving the Learning Process at SDN 205 Neglasari, Bandung City, and how good school principal supervision management can improve the Learning Process maximally or optimally.

The specific aim of this research is to describe the picture/information and analyze about; 1) Academic Supervision Management Planning using Guidance Principles in Improving Pedagogical Competency at SDN 205 Neglasari Bandung 2) Organizing Academic Supervision Management Planning using Guidance Principles in Improving Pedagogical Competency at SDN 205 Neglasari Bandung, 3) Academic Supervision Management Planning

using Guidance Principles in Improving Pedagogical Competence at SDN 205 Neglasari Bandung 4) Academic Supervision Management Planning using Guidance Principles in Improving Pedagogical Competency at SDN 205 Neglasari Bandung City. The results of this research are expected to provide benefits: 1) this paper on teacher academic supervision management can provide insight for the author and can be used as a guideline for developing teachers in schools so that teachers can improve their pedagogic competence well 2) it is hoped that it can be used as an academic reference and can be input for developing academic supervision development activities at the school. 3) For the community, it can be used as a forum for developing teachers in improving their academic competence so that they can improve the learning process.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a descriptive method because the descriptive method is very effective for analyzing data that is not measurable and is carried out in a natural setting. The method uses objective representation of reality or can also be interpreted as describing the object of research, tracking, carrying out systematics on a problem related to the object of research. This research attempts to describe management in improving the pedagogical competence of teachers at SDN 205 Neglasari.

1. Preparation phase

The preparation stage is the initial stage in conducting research. The steps taken at this stage are the preparation of a proposal containing a research design. In this step the researcher is guided by the accompanying lecturer, which is then approved and can then be developed by the author in accordance with the theory and research methods used.

At this preparation stage, the author also prepares an interview guide sheet and observation guide and prepares a research permit letter from the relevant agency for the smooth running of the author's further research.

2. Implementation Level

The Implementation Stage is the stage of extracting in-depth data information from related parties. Using interview guidelines, observation guidelines and documentation studies created at the preparation stage, the author gets to know the object more deeply. In the interview guide, observation guide and documentation study, researchers use questions, observation guide and documentation study that are in accordance with the research objectives and questions.

3. Reporting Stage

At this reporting stage the author carries out data triangulation activities which is a check or inspection of the data obtained in order to obtain the validity of the data. At this stage, a comparison is also made between the results of observations and interviews and comparing them with information obtained from other people close to the respondent. The author prepared a report on the results of data collection, namely the results of observations and interviews. After preparing this report, research results were obtained in compiling a report on matters

related to the aims and objectives of the research which were then prepared systematically based on reporting procedures.

4. Data Collection Techniques

The data collection technique for this research is using techniques *sampling*, This means that the researcher selects certain respondents who represent all respondents. This selection is based on several things such as: *background* Respondents are expected to be able to provide as much data as is appropriate to the research question.

Based on the source of data collection, researchers use primary data, namely data obtained directly from the object under study through data collection procedures and techniques in the form of observation, interviews and documentation studies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The organization of this academic supervision program which is carried out by the school principal to carry out the planning of a program is carried out with strategy and effectiveness regarding communication and coordination, namely by selecting and arranging a small committee to implement the program.

In terms of organization, for this purpose instructions are given and *job description* clear. SDN 205 Neglasari proves this with the Principal's Decree regarding the committee.

Usually in the decree made by the school principal, only the chairman, secretary and treasurer are included. These three people will be *leading persons* who will select effective and efficient committee members. Communication will be built when a large committee is formed

In this research, researchers found that the academic supervision program provides targets for each teacher so that they can achieve good performance. Each program must be planned, implemented and evaluated professionally, effectively and efficiently. The involvement of all PTK potentials must be a means of 'showing competence' or developing the competence of all school human resources.

Evaluations carried out by school principals and development supervisors regarding the implementation and achievement of an activity must be based on data obtained in the field and experienced by those implementing the activity. The school principal, so that improvements for the next activity program will be achieved. The most important thing in an evaluation of the implementation of school activities or programs is the follow-up for improvements in future school activities. The principal, supervisors and teachers carry out evaluations and make efforts to establish good cooperation between the principal, committee and teachers.

CONCLUSION

Academic supervision management in terms of program planning, organizing all school potential or school human resources, program implementation and program evaluation carried out by the school principal will determine the achievement of the planned school program.

Researchers can conclude from the results of research at SDN 205 Neglasari as follows:

1. The planning of the academic supervision program implemented at SDN 205 Neglasari Bandung was correct. The principal, supervisor, deputy head of curriculum and PTK supervisor and do it together with all school members, carried out at the beginning of the learning year, and there are specific targets planned in accordance with the school's mission perspective in this academic year
2. The supervision program is not only a planner, but is also involved in organizing school programs. The principal is involved in all school activities as the person in charge. The school principal is in each committee's WhatsApp group, so he can organize plans that have been made at the beginning of the year at the organizing level.
3. The supervision program is implemented by previously forming a small committee selected by the school principal. This small committee is formed as a large committee and with appropriate delegation, the activity program is implemented.
4. The implementation of activities is carried out by the school principal and a small committee is under the supervision of the school principal to provide quality standards for the implementation of school programs that should be implemented.
5. Evaluation of activities carried out by the school principal after implementation is used as data to improve subsequent program activities.
6. Teacher achievement that shows good PTK performance is determined by how a school principal can manage all teacher potential and the stages of implementing school activities, namely *planning*, *organizing*, *actuating* and *controlling* involving the school principal in it as a leader, motivator, quality control and so that activities run effectively and efficiently.

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